

The map behind the roadmap: Introducing a geospatial energy model for utility-scale solar and wind power buildout

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Summary

In many regions, energy models are pointing towards variable renewable energy (VRE), mainly solar photovoltaics (PV) and wind power, as potential backbone of future power systems. However, such models have not typically been able to explicitly include, from the outset, geospatial aspects around future VRE power plant siting in the cost-optimisation. For instance, should one build far from the grid in search of excellent resources, or rather stay close to existing infrastructure to keep costs low? Here, we present an OSeMOSYS-FlexTool workflow for capacity expansion and dispatch optimisation that explicitly includes the geospatial dimension of VRE buildout. Applying the model to Kenya, we identify clear but nontrivial links between site characteristics and siting preferences in the optimisation results, which moreover differ markedly for solar PV and wind power. This highly replicable approach has important implications for power system planning, especially in countries whose grids will be VRE-heavy in the future.

Introduction

For a successful transition to sustainable power systems that enable access to low-cost electricity for all, a strong expansion of power generation capacity will be required across the world to meet rising

demand. The main drivers of rising demand are (i) ongoing economic development alongside population growth, in particular in many developing nations¹, and (ii) the required drive for end-use electrification in transport, buildings, and industry as nations embark on pathways towards decarbonisation².

To attain such a long-term expansion of power systems, various stages of planning are required. For instance, the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) recommends four subsequent stages^{3,4}:

- (i) long-term planning exercises (several decades into the future) to obtain scenarios on possible low-cost combinations of power generating sources constituting an adequate power mix;
- (ii) geospatial planning exercises to determine where to build the power plants constituting the aforementioned mix, and to determine how and where to build out the grid;
- (iii) dispatch studies (at hourly or sub-hourly timescale) to ascertain that the suggested power mix would be robust across variable situations of demand and supply availability;
- (iv) grid studies (at sub-second timescale) to study the static and dynamic stability of the grid under extreme situations and allow contingency planning.

Each of these stages typically requires its own dedicated modelling tools and methodologies. For instance, the academic literature has firmly established cost-optimisation models as appropriate for the long-term planning of stage (i), and a substantial body of literature has developed around the use of models such as OSeMOSYS, LEAP, EnergyPLAN, SPLAT-MESSAGE, TIMES, and others which are now seen as standard. In general, there is an ongoing trend of moving to models with higher spatiotemporal resolution⁵⁻⁸, necessary in the face of strong growth of variable renewable energy (VRE) sources in recent years. Simultaneously, there is another trend of moving towards more open-source solutions to allow for more straightforward use of these models by policy planners and practitioners^{9,10}.

Despite this growing body of work, various regions of the world still suffer from a lack of attention by the research community. In particular, the African continent is currently the least-covered in terms of energy modelling studies at the country-level^{11,12}, despite having both the world's fastest-growing demand and the world's highest need for energy access growth and grid buildout^{13,14}. Given the latter challenges, energy models—which were originally largely designed in and adopted for European and North American geographies, where the same challenges do not necessarily apply—typically require certain adaptations to be suitable for use in most countries in Africa¹⁴.

This divergence of model requirements between Europe/North America on one hand, and Africa on the other, becomes clear when considering the combination of stage (i) above (long-term planning) with stage (ii) (geospatial planning) and stage (iii) (dispatch planning). Energy modelling exercises for countries across Africa, as for many other parts of the world, nowadays tend to point towards solar photovoltaics (PV) and (depending on geography) wind power as the most promising future technologies to meet growing power demand, supported by hydropower and geothermal where available, alongside a strong drive towards grid strengthening, interconnections, and storage solutions^{1,15-20}. But as opposed to other parts of the world, many African countries are not currently in a position for the solar and wind power buildout that such long-term planning models may suggest, as they face continued challenges with relatively weak grids with low levels of inertia, low spatial buildout of grids covering only limited parts of national territories, and high costs of capital for VRE technologies^{13,14}, as starting points. These challenges impact all stages mentioned above, from long-term planning to short-term planning to geospatial planning. Thus, the classical method, in which these are separate and subsequent planning exercises feeding into each other, is likely not sufficient in many

African country contexts and would lead to sub-optimal planning. This could be avoided by unifying them as much as possible within one single approach^{13,14}.

This implies that long-term planning—which tends to suggest high future shares of VRE—should, *from the outset*, account for geospatial planning (where should the suggested VRE be built, taking into account constraints dictated by e.g. land access/use, terrain, and distance from existing infrastructure?), dispatch planning (how should the rest of the system operate as VRE keeps growing, and where will flexibility come from?) and grid expansion planning (among other questions, how to ensure there is sufficient inertia in the growing system at all times?). The geospatial elements of VRE buildout and concurrent grid expansion are evidently crucial in unifying these different planning elements.

Yet, so far, a consistent approach to unify geospatial VRE planning into one framework with long-term planning and dispatch planning has been lacking in energy modelling literature, leading to possible discrepancies at the African country level between long-term visions (typically, strong VRE expansions) and on-the-ground spatial power sector planning (often characterised by hesitations to prioritise VRE, both due to grid stability concerns in the context of relative inadequacy of existing grid infrastructure, and due to absence of grid infrastructure in locations with attractive VRE resources)^{13,14}. While recent progress has been made to improve geospatial representation in energy models for Uganda²¹ and Kenya²², the main focus in those works was modelling on-grid and off-grid expansion within the same framework, and they did not consider the geospatial element of utility-scale VRE expansion in optimised long-term and dispatch planning.

The above-mentioned challenge of where to focus utility-scale VRE power plant buildout spatially has thus still remained largely untouched, preventing African countries from drawing up spatially explicit priority roadmaps to attract investment for VRE plants, and concurrent masterplans for grid expansion. Elsewhere, such roadmaps are already common, as seen from e.g. the Dutch government's recently published spatial offshore wind roadmap²³.

Approach

In this study, we present a new state-of-the-art method to combine capacity expansion planning, geospatial power system planning, and dispatch planning into a single coherent approach, essentially merging the main elements of stages (i)-(iii) above into a single simplified workflow. We demonstrate this approach through an OSeMOSYS-FlexTool workflow for Kenya, where recent work has suggested solar and wind power are set to become the dominant power generating sources by 2050²⁴. For details on this workflow, the reader is referred to “*Experimental Procedures*”, sub-section “*OSeMOSYS-FlexTool linkage*”.

We chose Kenya as a case study for two reasons. Firstly, the potential for both solar photovoltaics (PV) and wind power in Kenya is high and both tend to emerge as “backbone” sources for Kenya's grid according to classical capacity expansion studies²⁴, in line with Kenya's commitments towards decarbonising²⁵. Secondly, Kenya faces ongoing challenges in its power sector, in particular the challenge of blackouts, which have recently been linked to insufficient holistic planning in the wake of increasing VRE penetration, with e.g. loss of generation at the Lake Turkana Wind Power Plant having been blamed for nationwide outages^{26,27}. This indicates an imminent need for a comprehensive method integrating capacity expansion planning, geospatial planning, and dispatch planning.

For this study, we upgraded an existing OSeMOSYS-FlexTool workflow for Kenya (see ref. ²⁴ for details) by including spatially explicit information on potential VRE locations—including location-dependent resource strength and temporal power generation profiles, site-specific transmission grid and road

network expansion costs, and terrain-constrained available land area for each location—in the optimisation procedure, according to the “Model Supply Regions” (MSR) approach developed by IRENA²⁸. Essentially, instead of using a single representative technology for solar PV and wind power each among the investment options in the capacity expansion model, we split the investment options for solar and wind in the model up into spatially disaggregated clusters—ten for solar and ten for wind—each with their own characteristic power generation profiles, their own characteristic transmission grid and road network expansion costs to link them to existing infrastructures, and their own specific maximum deployment potential according to constraints dictated by the terrain. For details, the reader is referred to “*Experimental Procedures*”, sub-section “*Representation of solar and wind investment options*”.

Subsequently, by explicitly linking $N-1$ system security constraints²⁹ and inertia constraints²⁴ to the spatially divergent VRE expansion options both in OSeMOSYS and FlexTool, the workflow integrated long-term capacity expansion scenarios on one hand with hourly-scale dispatch scenarios for individual years on the other. (Again, see “*Experimental Procedures*”, sub-section “*Representation of solar and wind investment options*” for details.) This allowed to produce coherent scenarios merging the short-term, long-term, and geospatial elements of planning. In this way, credible geospatial investment roadmaps for utility-scale solar and wind power expansion for Kenya could be drawn up.

This is, to our knowledge, the first such application of geospatially explicit information in a coupled long-term capacity expansion and short-term dispatch workflow. While Kenya is used here as case study, given that the approach and implementation are fully based on open-source workflows and datasets, the same principle could be readily applied to any other country in Africa or other regions.

Most of the assumptions have been chosen in collaboration with the Least Cost Power Development Plan (LCPDP) team of the Kenyan Ministry of Energy and Petroleum, which produces the medium and long-term plan focusing on generation and transmission for the Kenyan power system^{30,31}. One of the authors of this paper (M.A.) was part of the LCPDP team during the conception of this paper.

Results

In this section, the results of the OSeMOSYS-FlexTool modelling application with MSR-based solar and wind clusters, applied to the Kenyan context, are described. We first show the results of the capacity expansion modelling with OSeMOSYS for the period up to 2050. Subsequently, we analyse in more detail the characteristics of the spatial selection preference for solar and wind clusters, and their selection order, in the OSeMOSYS results. Last, we present the results of the flexibility analysis using FlexTool, based on the capacity mix suggested by OSeMOSYS for the marker years 2030 and 2050.

Power system capacities in OSeMOSYS

In Figure 1, we show the evolution of the Kenyan power sector towards 2050 for two demand scenarios modelled with OSeMOSYS. Both demand projections are obtained from Kihara et al.²⁴; the low demand scenario (denoted with S1) is based on historical growth rates and results in an average year-on-year growth rate of 5.3%, while the high demand scenario (S2) is consistent with all targets of the Vision 2030 development program being met³², projecting the same average annual growth of 8.2% until 2050.

Three phases can be identified in the evolution of the power system.

The first few years are reflective of the current situation in Kenya, characterised by the occurrence of blackouts partly caused by insufficient capacity. Indeed, the capacity available to the model between 2019 and 2025, constrained by existing capacity and committed projects as per Kenya's Medium-Term

Plan³⁰, is not enough to meet the capacity requirements of the system, and OSeMOSYS is forced to install some fictitious backstop capacity (see black wedge in graph). However, from 2026 the capacity buildout constraints in the model are relaxed, and the model is free to install enough new capacity to meet the extra power needs. The bigger contribution to the early expansion of the system is given by batteries, which provide two distinct services to the grid. Firstly, batteries help meet the reserve margin needs. Based on the LCPDP team planning procedures, a 10% reserve margin is imposed across the model time horizon, meaning that the total installed firm capacity has to exceed by 10% the annual peak power demand. Batteries are allowed to contribute to the fulfilment of the reserve margin, and are hence invested in by the model to solve the grid issues as soon as they become available (see Table S1 for an overview of all technologies' reserve margin contribution). The second way in which batteries contribute to the expansion of the system is by redispatching the energy produced by VRE, mostly wind turbines at this point of the model time horizon. The amount of energy stored and then redistributed by batteries is shown in purple in the lower panel of Figure 1. In both demand scenarios, battery activity surges around 2025 to reach a first peak in activity between 2030 and 2035.

Natural gas power plants are not permitted to come online before 2030 in the model, as Kenya is currently lacking any type of gas infrastructure. New capacity is considered to be based on liquified natural gas (LNG) imports, and the way in which the relative costs are considered is outlined in "*Experimental Procedures*", subsection "*OSeMOSYS description*". From 2030 onwards, natural gas capacity starts to be added, progressively replacing the first wave of battery installations as they are retired. As was the case for batteries in the 2020s, gas power plants are mostly built to satisfy the reserve margin requirements, and this can be seen by comparing the share of natural gas in installed capacity (upper panel in Figure 1) to the share of natural gas in electricity generation (second row panel in Figure 1). In the former case, natural gas reaches a peak share of 23% in 2038 in the low-demand case and 29% in the high-demand one on a capacity basis, while the electricity production peaks from natural gas plants are limited to 5.3% and 7.8%, showing that the added natural gas capacities are idle for most of the year and used exclusively as peaking plants. The electricity generation mix from 2030 to 2040 is mostly composed of geothermal, hydro, and wind power.

The third and last phase of the evolution of the Kenyan power system starts around 2040, when the combination of solar PV and batteries becomes cost-competitive with geothermal and gas power plants. Most additional capacity requirement after 2040 is met by solar, wind, and batteries, reaching a total installed capacity of 26 GW (low-demand) and 55 GW (high-demand) in 2050, a manifold growth from the 2.7 GW in 2019.

Other minor trends that can be observed include the low reliance on imports from Ethiopia throughout the entire modelled period, despite 400 MW being available from 2026; the modest contribution from pumped hydro, limited by the 600 MW technical potential currently estimated by the LCPDP team; and fuel oil plants being completely retired in all scenarios before 2035.

In addition to these two scenarios, two additional scenarios were run in which the cost outlook for solar and wind power was somewhat less optimistic, to show the robustness of the obtained results even under potentially more adverse economic conditions for VRE. More information is provided in "*Experimental procedures*", sub-section "*Scenarios*", and results are shown in the Supplementary Information (Figure S1).

Figure 1. Power system capacities and levels of activity in OSeMOSYS.

OSeMOSYS results for the low (left column) and high (right column) demand scenarios. The first row shows the evolution of the installed capacity throughout the modelled time horizon, while the second row does the same for the actual energy produced by each power source. Rows three and four show the amount of energy stored and discharged each year by, respectively, pumped hydro and batteries. See also Figure S1 for additional scenarios.

Geospatial analysis of results

Having described the overall makeup of Kenya's capacity mix according to the OSeMOSYS results, we can now analyse the selection of solar and wind power clusters in greater detail, as well as the dynamics behind the model's preference for their buildout. We note that the buildout speed of VRE within each cluster is constrained according to $N-1$ security criteria (see "Experimental procedures", subsection "Representation of solar and wind investment options"), which prevents the model from concentrating all capacity in single locations with highly attractive conditions. This constraint therefore pushes the model to deploy VRE across multiple locations according to a priority ranking of clusters, typically starting with a single preferred region and progressively spreading across more and more clusters. A geospatial representation of the clusters included in the model workflow, adapted from Sterl et al. ^{28,33}, is provided in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2. Geospatial representation of the solar and wind clusters for Kenya.

The figure shows the clusters for solar PV (left) and wind power (right) included in the present OSeMOSYS-FlexTool workflow. The data on clusters is taken from the repository in ref. ³³ and re-visualised for purposes of this paper. The data on transmission and distribution grid is taken from GridFinder ³⁴. Note that the numbers of the clusters are arbitrarily assigned and do not signify any particular order of attractiveness. Both sets of clusters cover 5% of Kenya's territory, and the total potential for solar PV and wind power plant deployment across clusters adds up to 96 GW (solar) and 86 GW (wind).

Our aim here is to analyse the characteristics of this priority ranking and how it differs for solar and wind. We can assess the added value of the geospatial representation of solar and wind investment options through the MSR clusters, as compared to classical energy modelling approaches which lack this geospatial dimension. Such an added value is present *if, and only if*, the model selects solar and wind clusters in a *nontrivial* order; that is, if the selection preference for solar and wind clusters does *not* simply follow whichever cluster has the highest yield per unit of capacity (expressed through the average capacity factor CF).

In general, we can observe that this approach provides three distinguishing features of the individual clusters, which are distinctive from the standard OSeMOSYS approach: (1) the average resource strength (CF), (2) the supplementary costs for transmission grid and road buildout ($trCAPEX$), and (3) the temporal profile of the resource. Thus, if the model prefers selecting clusters in a given order, this order must be interpretable by examining the aforementioned three features.

Figure 3. Capacity buildout of the geospatially referenced solar and wind clusters.

MSR cluster buildout according to OSeMOSYS for the low (left) and high (right) demand scenarios. The first row shows the solar MSR cluster buildout and the second row the wind MSR cluster buildout. See also Figure S2 for additional scenarios.

The buildout of MSR clusters is shown visually in **Figure 3**, which provide a breakdown by cluster of the overall solar and wind buildout across Kenya already shown in **Figure 1**. In Table 1 and Table 2, we now show a detailed overview of the characteristics of all the solar and wind clusters selected by the model runs, in order of selection by the model. The tables include details on the buildout, notably their first year of operation and total capacity by 2050 according to OSeMOSYS results. Further, we show each cluster's average capacity factor (*CF*) and average supplementary CAPEX for grid and road buildout (*trCAPEX*). Last, the table includes a qualitative description of the geographical characteristics and the lay-of-the-land of each cluster.

Table 1: Solar PV clusters. Detailed description of the buildout timeline and distinguishing characteristics of the solar PV clusters in the model, ordered by their priority ranking as per the model's selection preference. A single asterisk (*) in the capacity column indicates that the capacity buildout by 2050 is constrained by N-1 criteria, whereas a double asterisk (**) indicates that the capacity buildout by 2050 is constrained by the size of the cluster and its potential is exhausted. Absence of an asterisk therefore indicates that buildout in the cluster has neither yet reached the maximum allowed by system security constraints nor the maximum spatial deployment potential within the cluster. S1 = scenario 1 (low demand), S2 = scenario 2 (high demand).

Cluster # (maximum capacity in GW)	First year	Capacity in 2050 (GW)	CF (%)	trCAPEX (USD/kW)	County	Qualitative description
Selected in all scenarios						
#10 (18.93)	2043 (S1) 2038 (S2)	0.95 (S1)* 1.97 (S2)*	21.4%	141.6	Marsabit, Samburu	Areas on the eastern side of the Rift Valley directly to the south of Lake Turkana. This cluster is partially coincident with wind clusters #4 and #9.
#1 (15.86)	2044 (S1) 2041 (S2)	0.95 (S1)* 1.97 (S2)*	21.0%	120.6	Laikipia, Samburu	Area on the highlands bordered to the north by Maralal town and the Loroghi Plateau, to the west by the Rift escarpment, and to the east by the western slopes of the Milgis river sub-basin.
#3 (12.74)	2044 (S1) 2041 (S2)	0.95 (S1)* 1.97 (S2)*	20.8%	122.1	Baringo, Elgeyo- Marakwet	Lower-lying areas of the Rift Valley as well as in the adjacent Kerio Valley, bounded by the B4 highway in the north and Lake Bogoria in the south.
#5 (8.69)	2045 (S1) 2042 (S2)	0.95 (S1)* 1.97 (S2)*	20.8%	128.5	West Pokot, Trans-Nzoia	Highland area along the Kenyan-Ugandan border roughly corresponding to the triangle between Mount Elgon in the southeast, Turkwell Dam in the north, and the Cherangani Hills in the southwest.
#2 (7.09)	2045 (S1) 2043 (S2)	0.45 (S1) 1.76 (S2)	20.8%	140.2	Kisumu, Homa Bay, Siaya, Busia	Lakeshore areas west and north of Kisumu straddling the shores of the shallow Winam Gulf. The authors note that there may be potential for deploying floating solar instead of ground-based solar here.
Not selected						
#4 (9.48)	-	-	21.2%	165.6	Narok	Area on the plateau directly southwest of Narok town, part of the Southern Ewaso Ng'iro basin, bounded in the south by the Maasai Mara National Reserve.
#6 (1.64)	-	-	20.6%	103.0	Uasin Gishu, Nandi	Areas on the plateau directly surrounding Eldoret town west of the Rift Valley.
#7 (7.32)	-	-	20.6%	107.4	Nakuru, Baringo	Southward continuation of cluster #3, comprising low-lying areas in the Rift Valley north and south of Naruku, roughly stretching from Lake Bogoria to Lake Naivasha.
#8 (2.73)	-	-	20.3%	88.3	Nandi, Kericho, Kisumu	The low-lying area stretching eastwards from Kisumu (Winam Gulf of Lake Victoria) up to the escarpment on the western side of the Rift Valley, sandwiched by higher-lying areas to the north (Nandi Hills) and south (Mau Forest).

#9 (11.11)	-	-	20.8%	104.6	Nyeri, Laikipia, Nyandarua	Similar to cluster #1 but further to the south, comprising areas in the highlands north of Mount Kenya and Aberdare National Parks. Coincide to some extent with wind cluster #5, in particular around Ol Pejeta Conservancy.
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Table 2: Wind clusters. Detailed description of the buildout timeline and distinguishing characteristics of the wind clusters in the model, ordered by their priority ranking as per the model's selection preference. A single asterisk (*) in the capacity column indicates that the capacity buildout by 2050 is constrained by N-1 criteria, whereas a double asterisk (**) indicates that the capacity buildout by 2050 is constrained by the size of the cluster and its potential is exhausted. Absence of an asterisk therefore indicates that buildout in the cluster has neither yet reached the maximum allowed by system security constraints nor the maximum spatial deployment potential within the cluster. S1 = scenario 1 (low demand), S2 = scenario 2 (high demand).

Cluster # (maximum capacity in GW)	First year	Capacity in 2050 (MW)	CF (%)	trCAPEX (USD/kW)	County	Qualitative description
Selected in all scenarios						
#4 (10.07)	2025 (S1) 2025 (S2)	0.95 (S1)* 1.97 (S2)*	55.4%	245.4	Marsabit	Areas directly straddling Lake Turkana on its eastern shore: the area south of Sibilo National Park and the area stretching from Loiyangalani town to the Lake's southern tip. Note that Lake Turkana Wind Power Plant is located in the latter zone.
#3 (12.61)	2030 (S1) 2025 (S2)	0.95 (S1)* 1.97 (S2)*	52.0%	285.1	Marsabit	Higher-lying areas surrounding Marsabit town, typically the lower slopes of mountains and hill ridges dotted across the area around (but not including) the Chalbi Desert. Wind speeds are somewhat higher at these altitudes than in cluster #1, but the terrain is more difficult.
#6 (5.74)	2034 (S1) 2025 (S2)	0.95 (S1)* 1.97 (S2)*	50.0%	218.5	Turkana, Marsabit	The area in Turkana Country between Lake Turkana's southwestern shore and the Kerio River, as well as a smaller area on the opposite lakeshore, on the ridges north of Loiyangalani town in Marsabit Country where the Lake's eastern shore curves sharply westward and where the shoreline itself lies in the ridges' wind shadow.
#10 (15.62)	2038 (S1) 2030 (S2)	0.95 (S1)* 1.97 (S2)*	45.1%	334.8	Marsabit	Area north of clusters #1, #3 and #4 on the eastern shore of Lake Turkana, stretching up to the Ethiopian border. This area is characterised by high wind speeds but much higher remoteness as compared to the other clusters in Marsabit county.
#5 (0.56)	2042 (S1) 2030 (S2)	0.56 (S1)** 0.56 (S2)**	40.7%	107.0	Laikipia, Meru	Areas around Mount Kenya National Park, in particular west of Mount Kenya straddling the Ol Pejeta Wildlife conservancy (a slight depression in the highlands) and north of Meru town. Coincides to some extent with solar cluster #9.

#7 (5.99)	2043 (S1) 2034 (S2)	0.95 (S1)* 1.97 (S2)*	41.2%	237.7	Isiolo	Areas directly north of the Nyambene hill ridge and south of the Ewaso Nyiro river, where the highlands start their drop towards the Indian Ocean. (There is an area with similar conditions at nearly identical longitude but more north in Marsabit Country where a similar drop towards sea level begins, but this area is harder to access.)
#1 (20.37)	2047 (S1) 2038 (S2)	0.95 (S1)* 1.97 (S2)*	41.8%	245.3	Marsabit	Lower-lying areas largely stretching between the hill ridges surrounding Marsabit town (which make up cluster #3), in particular the stretch from Marsabit town to North Horr town just north of the Chalbi Desert.
#2 (6.05)	2050 (S1) 2045 (S2)	0.49 (S1) 1.97 (S2)*	46.6%	191.2	Samburu, Turkana	Areas mostly adjacent to and directly west and south of cluster #9, along the transition of the Losiolo escarpment into the Suguta Valley, where katabatic winds result in a higher average wind speed than cluster #9 but the locations are more scattered and harder to access.
Additionally selected in high demand scenario						
#9 (7.28)	2048 (S2)	1.97 (S2)*	42.4%	148.6	Samburu	Area just east of the Losiolo escarpment on the east side of the Rift Valley, roughly ranging in a north-south line from the southern tip of Lake Turkana to Malaso, interrupted by Mount Ng'iro, with the Suguta Valley to the west.
Not selected						
#8 (1.64)	-	-	40.5%	103.4	Kajiado	Area running north-south straddling the escarpment on the east side of the Rift Valley, starting around the Ngong Hills down to the latitude of Lake Magadi down in the Rift Valley. Note that Ngong Hills wind power station is located here.

This overview allows for an in-depth assessment of why certain locations are preferred to others. Looking first at solar PV (Table 1), it is clear that the selection order does *not* trivially follow the resource strength, and that distance from infrastructure plays an important role. For instance, although the highest-*CF* solar cluster (#10, with *CF* = 21.4%) is selected first, the second-highest *CF* solar cluster (#4, with *CF* = 21.2) is never selected, which can be explained by its remoteness and therefore prohibitively high *trCAPEX*.

The decisiveness of *trCAPEX* in certain cases is observed most clearly among selected solar clusters with highly similar *CF*, such as solar clusters #2, #3 and #5 which all exhibit a *CF* = 20.8%. Here, the order of selection appears to be determined by the *trCAPEX* parameter, with solar cluster #3 being selected earlier than solar cluster #5 (which has a 5% higher *trCAPEX*) and solar cluster #2 (which has a 15% higher *trCAPEX*). In other words, since there is nothing to be gained in *average* yield by changing between solar clusters #2, #3 and #5, and since the temporal profiles of these clusters have relatively similar seasonal profile shapes (with all three clusters lying in the westernmost part of Kenya, cf. **Figure 2**), the determining factor for cluster preference becomes their distance from the existing infrastructure (and the associated additional cost for grid and road expansion), with locations closer to existing assets being preferred.

Yet, *trCAPEX* is not always the determining factor. For instance, we see in Table 1 that solar cluster #9 also has the same *CF* = 20.8%, as well as a lower *trCAPEX* than the three aforementioned solar clusters (14% lower than solar cluster #3), yet still is not selected. It is here that we observe that the shape of the profiles also plays a role in the selection process. To explain the non-selection of solar cluster #9, we need to draw solar cluster #1 into the discussion, which is geographically contiguous to #9 (**Figure 2**). In this case, we observe that solar cluster #1 has a higher capacity factor than solar cluster #9 (which makes up for its somewhat higher *trCAPEX*), aside from which its temporal profile is nearly indistinguishable from #9 due to their close geographical proximity. Together, these factors result in a higher overall economic attractiveness to build in solar cluster #1 as compared to solar cluster #9. Once substantial capacity exists in solar cluster #1, there is no reason for the model to build in solar cluster #9, which has no real distinguishing features from #1 except for being more expensive per unit of produced electricity. Solar clusters #2, #3 and #5, on the other hand, while exhibiting the same average resource strength as solar cluster #9, lie further to the west than #1 and #9 and therefore produce power until somewhat later in the evening, providing an added value in terms of diversifying the mix by correlating better with evening demand than solar cluster #9. In summary, the model builds in solar cluster #1 (owing to its high *CF*) and in solar clusters #2, #3 and #5 (owing to their correlation to demand, and in an order determined by *trCAPEX*), but refrains from building in solar cluster #9 (which is neither as strong as solar cluster #1 nor as synergetic to demand as solar clusters #2, #3 and #5).

Thus, it is shown that the selection preference for solar PV clusters is *nontrivial* as it does not follow the resource yield solely, and all three distinguishing features mentioned earlier (*CF*, *trCAPEX*, and temporal profiles) play a role. The added value of the geospatially referenced representation of solar PV clusters to find cost-optimal solutions is therefore evident.

Next, we turn to the wind results (Table 2). The higher geospatial variation of wind power potential as compared to solar PV across Kenya's territory means that the distance from existing infrastructures is less of an impediment to the attractiveness of developing wind sites vis-à-vis solar PV²⁸. In other words, expanding existing infrastructures to connect a wind "goldmine" in a remote region may be more readily worth the effort as compared to solar PV. This is evidenced by e.g. the three wind clusters with highest *CF* coming in first, second and third place in the selection order, despite having among the highest *trCAPEX* observed among wind clusters. Thus, at very high *CF*, it appears that *trCAPEX* plays no role and resource strength is indeed decisive. Incidentally, cluster #4 (the first selected wind cluster) is the location of Kenya's existing Lake Turkana Wind Power Project, Africa's largest wind power plant, providing somewhat of a real-life reflection of the preceding statement.

Nevertheless, the relationship between wind cluster selection order and wind power *CF* is not trivial. For instance, wind cluster #5 comes fifth in the selection order, despite having the second-lowest *CF* of all. Its selection before other clusters with higher *CF* appears to be linked to its *trCAPEX*, which is second-lowest among all wind clusters and thus partially compensates the low *CF*. Yet, this does not appear to point to any general trend, as wind cluster #8 has a similar *CF* and a similar *trCAPEX* as wind cluster #5 and yet is never selected.

Analysing their temporal profiles, we observe that the *CF* time series of wind cluster #5 exhibits a much lower coefficient of variation (0.29) as compared to wind cluster #8 (0.36, the highest of all clusters) at the time-slice level (note that the same is also true at full hourly level). The lower coefficient of variation of wind cluster #5 thus translates into a less "variable" (and arguably more "baseload-like") resource in the model, requiring less additional investment in flexibility, and makes wind cluster #5 preferable to wind cluster #8, even though in terms of *CF* and *trCAPEX*, the two are hard to distinguish. In other words: despite the relative mediocrity of its resource, wind cluster #5 has favourable cost

parameters thanks to its closeness to existing infrastructure, and while this also applies to wind cluster #8, the latter's resource is too variable to be attractive to the system.

We note here that even though all selected wind clusters are at their maximum allowed capacity by 2050 in the high-demand scenario, the model still does not select wind cluster #8. This is because by 2050, solar PV and batteries have become so cheap that wind cluster #8, with its unfavourable resource variability, is unattractive not only in comparison with other wind clusters, but also with solar cluster #2 in combination with batteries (the only active solar cluster which is not yet "maxed out" by 2050).

A similar argument as for wind cluster #5 vis-à-vis #8 (above) can be made for the competition between wind clusters #10 and #2. Wind cluster #2 comes only in eighth place in the selection order, despite having the fourth-highest *CF* overall, whereas wind cluster #10 has a somewhat lower *CF* and a much higher *trCAPEX* and yet is selected more than a decade earlier than #2. Despite its less favourable cost parameters, wind cluster #10 has a more constant resource throughout the year than #2 (coefficient of variation of 0.22 for the former's time-sliced profile, as compared to 0.29 for the latter), and perhaps more importantly, #10 exhibits exquisite seasonal synergy with demand (with a correlation coefficient of 0.95 between the seasonal profiles of cluster #10 and demand, as compared to only 0.55 for #2 whose resource has a much more unfavourable seasonality). Therefore, building in wind cluster #10 is preferable as it requires less investment in additional flexibility and seasonal balancing as compared to wind cluster #2 (although in the end the latter is also built).

Thus, as for solar PV, it is shown that the selection preference for wind clusters is *nontrivial*. Although the very highest-*CF* clusters do tend to be selected first regardless of remoteness, outside of these "top" resource locations the relationship between *CF*, *trCAPEX*, and profile shapes becomes intricate. Thus, the added value of the geospatially referenced representation through MSR clusters is again showcased.

The observed trends are robust under less optimistic assumptions for the future cost reductions of solar and wind power, as shown in the two additional high-cost scenarios that were run. The results show that going to more pessimistic capital cost projections for VRE does not change the order of VRE cluster selection, it only delays the onset of large-scale VRE buildout by several years. Results can be consulted in Supplementary Figures S1-S2.

Flexibility analysis

When analysed in FlexTool, both scenarios show similar results for 2030. The model's optimal dispatch plan identifies only one flexibility challenge, the lack of inertia in the system, which amounts to 0.2% of the requirement for both cases. There are no curtailments in both scenarios. To solve the lack of inertia, the investment mode of the model suggests additional investments in natural gas and hydropower capacity in both cases (see **Figure 4**). Notably, no new transmission line investments between the regions of Kenya's power system areas (Western, Nairobi, Mt. Kenya, and Coast) are recommended for 2030.

Figure 4. Additional generation capacities identified by FlexTool.

Additional generation capacities suggested by FlexTool for 2030 and 2050 on top of the OSeMOSYS results to deal with flexibility challenges at the dispatch level. There is also additional investment in transmission capacities between different regions of the Kenyan grid, which are described in the text but not shown here.

In the low-demand case, for 2050, FlexTool reveals more substantial flexibility challenges in the dispatch planning of the power plants. While the core issue remains insufficient inertia (although less than 0.1% of the requirement), minor loss of load (0.07% of demand) and reserve deficiencies (0.6% of demand) also occur. Curtailment of VRE rises considerably to 26%.

FlexTool’s investment mode recommends a mix of power capacity additions (**Figure 4**) to address these issues. (For a more detailed explanation of what “investment mode” entails, see Kihara et al.²⁴) Natural gas (0.8 GW), nuclear (0.9 GW) and hydropower (0.7 GW) are introduced to tackle the lack of inertia thanks to their high inertia constants (see Table S2) (0.1 GW) corresponding to the High Grand Falls dam is suggested for its ability to provide flexibility, inertia, and reserves. These investments eliminate flexibility issues and reduce curtailment to 10%, as demonstrated in **Figure 5**.

The Invest graph (i.e. dispatch including additional investments suggested by FlexTool) in **Figure 5** shows a flexible operation of nuclear and geothermal power plants, with periods lasting several hours of complete shutdown before ramping up again to minimum load or higher. This optimised dispatch plan is the result of the following constraints: a minimum hourly load of 50% and 75% for nuclear and geothermal respectively, minimum up and down times of 48 hours and 1 hour, and ramp-up and ramp-down rate limitations of 1% and 2-3% of capacity per min. In this light, further analysis is recommended on the feasibility on the suggested capacity additions, since e.g. the frequent shutdown of nuclear power plants in these results requires more scrutiny.

However, we note here that the precise mix of natural gas, geothermal, and nuclear capacity suggested by FlexTool is of secondary importance for the results presented here. The main point is that additional capacity to the tune of 2-3 GW from units capable of providing baseload and flexibility, *such as* natural gas units, geothermal plants, or nuclear plants, would be necessary to allow the VRE-heavy mix suggested by OSeMOSYS to be realistic.

Figure 5. FlexTool dispatch profiles.

Dispatch of the power plants in the low-demand scenario for 2050, before (*Base*) and after (*Invest*) investments suggested by FlexTool.

In the high-demand case, for 2050, there are no flexibility issues, but curtailment of variable renewable energy rises to a substantial 32% of generation. However, FlexTool's investment mode still suggests some additional capacities (**Figure 4**) leading to a lower operational cost of the system: 7.4 billion dollars instead of 8.4 billion dollars before the investments. Curtailment slightly decreases to 31%, thanks to investments in transmission lines. This relatively high amount of remaining curtailment could be potentially reduced by including exports in the model, which is currently not possible with FlexTool. Moreover, the current investment mode does not penalise curtailments, which does not incentivise the model to invest in storage solutions like batteries, which could further reduce curtailment in dispatch mode. Investments in new transmission lines between the Nairobi, Mt. Kenya, and Coast regions amount to 1.2 GW, around 15% of the base-year capacities. The primary focus is on strengthening the Coast-Nairobi line with 0.8 GW, with the remaining on the Mt. Kenya-Coast line with 0.4 GW.

Discussion and results

This study describes the successful creation of a capacity expansion and dispatch optimisation model based on OSeMOSYS and FlexTool with the explicit inclusion of geospatially differentiated investment options for VRE. The result is a model that not only produces scenarios on *how much* VRE capacity to deploy in a country system in the future but also *where* and *in which spatial sequence* to build this capacity.

Applying the model to a case study for Kenya, the results show that, in terms of site selection, preferences are nontrivial in the sense that they are *not* necessarily determined by the capacity factor of the resource, which is the result that one would have expected from a classical model that does not have a geospatial differentiation of costs based on infrastructure expansion needs. For both solar PV and wind power, the site selection preference in a cost-optimised portfolio is a function of resource strength, grid expansion needs, and temporal profiles, with none of the three factors decisive by itself, the exception being the very top wind speed locations where resource strength defaults to being the sole factor of importance.

In the Kenyan case, our scenarios suggest that solar PV and wind power may jointly come to form the backbone of Kenya's future power system. The solar PV and wind resources will be preferentially spread across different parts of the country following the aforementioned factors, and will be backed up by geothermal power plants, natural gas power plants, battery storage, and pumped hydro storage. While this is in general agreement with previous work in ref.²⁴, various options exist to improve the work, which we touch upon below.

First, with the main focus of this study being the inclusion of the geospatially referenced VRE clusters in the model, going forward, we propose that more research is required to ensure all other technologies are also represented at the appropriate level of detail and ascertain that the suggested mix of technologies in this study is both plausible and practical. This refers principally to the future costs of technologies such as natural gas plants (requiring LNG import infrastructure to be built out in Kenya), pumped hydropower plants and their potential siting, new geothermal projects and their infrastructural needs, et cetera.

Second, the model used here considered Kenya as a mostly islanded system, with existing interconnections to neighbours such as Ethiopia modelled, but no opportunity for the model to invest in other cross-border interconnections. In the future, the model could be upgraded to include these potential links and examine effects of large VRE expansion on power trade with neighbouring regions.

Third, it could be argued that the costs of grid expansion for selecting optimal solar and wind clusters should itself be dynamic functions of VRE buildout within the model. For instance, as the first clusters get selected and investments in transmission lines to link them to the existing grid are made, other nearby clusters technically would see their distance-from-grid parameter drop from their initial value. Such a dynamic update of grid extension CAPEX is, however, not considered in the present model, the main argument being as follows. Imagine two clusters, A and B, which both lie along the same direction from the nearest existing grid connection point, but B at double the distance from the grid as A. If the model selects cluster A for VRE buildout and grid connection in a certain year, the distance from B to the "existing grid" would in theory halve subsequently, the grid having already been built out up to A. But a buildout of VRE in B would still require the same investments in *transmission capacity* as before, across the same distance as before—as the investments made by the model in transmission infrastructure connecting cluster A will only evacuate up to the maximum capacity of cluster A, and thus not be sufficient to accommodate cluster B unless more transmission capacity across the entire distance from cluster B to the initial grid is built.

Fourth, at the geospatial level, we further recommend on-the-ground fieldwork for each of the suggested VRE buildout clusters from the model to ascertain the extent to which conditions there may be appropriate for the construction of utility-scale solar PV and wind power projects. This needs to consider the social, cultural, and ecological dimensions of planning potential megaprojects in areas shared with human settlements, agricultural activities, and biodiversity hotspots, or access to which would require traversing terrain with such elements. While the Model Supply Regions approach principally excludes from the outset any protected areas, restricted areas, or areas with unsuitable land use, this is only a first high-level exclusion that may not be able to capture many on-the-ground elements, such as local opposition to megaprojects, or wildlife migration corridors impacted by the projects. We comment that, if necessary, it is possible to re-run the analysis leading to the solar and wind cluster creation with stricter exclusion criteria in case this would turn out to be necessary.

Fifth, the workflow presented here only considered on-grid systems, but possibilities may exist to soft-link the present model with geospatially-referenced models for off-grid electrification, such as OnSSET. In such a setup, OnSSET would help to assess the demand that could be met by the grid versus off-grid

solutions, while the OSeMOSYS-FlexTool workflow assesses the cost of grid electricity, which would in its turn be an explicit input into ONSSET. The fact that OSeMOSYS-FlexTool would itself have an explicit geospatial component in this setup, would help to more clearly distinguish areas where the grid would arrive in the future from areas that may remain uncovered by utility-scale infrastructure.

Sixth, we stress the importance of not seeing the current model results as a fixed outcome, but rather as a snapshot in a type of study that requires periodic updating to keep track with developments on the ground. As various external factors (outside of VRE cluster selection) lead to an expansion of Kenya's grid infrastructure, which areas are considered "close" and "far" from the existing infrastructure may organically change in the coming decades, with associated implications for the outcomes of site selection priorities by the present model. Thus, a periodic updating of all data inputs is recommended to keep abreast of concurrent developments. To support this, the authors have made the input data for OSeMOSYS and FlexTool used for this study publicly available (see "*Experimental procedures*", sub-section "*Resource availability*"), and will strive to undertake capacity building with relevant stakeholders in the data and model use.

As stated in the Introduction, one of the principal goals of this study was to generate insights to allow governments to set up spatially explicit priority roadmaps to attract investment for VRE plants, with beneficiaries being primarily private investors as well as local and international finance institutions. We believe that these stakeholders may be the primary target groups of the information and approach shown in this study. In this spirit, the author team will next work on setting up a data visualisation infrastructure to interactively present the geospatial outcomes of the current study, to be embedded within the Energy Access Explorer (www.energyaccessexplorer.org) to enhance integrated and inclusive energy planning at both national and subnational level in Kenya and to inform the upcoming Kenya National Electrification Strategy.

Finally, we emphasise the high replicability of this kind of study to other country contexts. The MSR methodology has already been used to generate results on siting options for solar and wind plants for all of continental Africa and also, more recently, Central and South America³⁵, and as such any country-level energy modelling exercise on those continents could readily be extended to include the present geospatial explicitness. We hope that further initiatives will take up this dimension in the future.

Experimental procedures

OSeMOSYS-FlexTool linkage

This paper uses a combined modelling approach to analyse the Kenyan power system, by leveraging the strengths of two open-source energy system models: OSeMOSYS and FlexTool.

The Open-Source energy Modelling SYStem (OSeMOSYS) is a cost-optimisation model for long-term energy planning, driven by the energy demand³⁶. It relies on a detailed bottom-up description of the energy system encompassing technologies, resources, and energy carriers. The model uses linear programming to optimise the total cost of the energy system, subject to a set of constraints representing technical or environmental limits. OSeMOSYS leverages a community of practice built around three pillars, namely, a code management structure, a community forum, and outreach activities³⁷. The full documentation for the model is available online³⁸.

FlexTool is a power system optimisation model developed by IRENA^{3,39}, which uses linear programming to solve the unit commitment and economic dispatch problem. The model provides the least-cost optimisation dispatch of power plants with a detailed assessment of potential issues linked to power system flexibility including curtailment, loss of load, excess load or insufficient reserves and inertia.

Beyond the dispatch problem, FlexTool can also select the least-cost investment options to address the identified flexibility issues. The model assumes perfect foresight, typically using a time resolution of one hour or less. Additionally, FlexTool is an open-source model and freely accessible for broader use⁴⁰.

OSeMOSYS is particularly suited for long-term planning as it optimises the energy system for the entire horizon. On the other hand, FlexTool optimises at an hourly level within a single year, incorporating detailed power system operational constraints not included in OSeMOSYS. The soft-linking between the two models allows FlexTool to complement the OSeMOSYS analysis, which has a much-reduced representation of flexibility.

As described in Kihara et al.²⁴, the soft-linking process relies on a bidirectional exchange of information. For each chosen marker year (the years for which FlexTool is run based on OSeMOSYS results for that year to identify potential flexibility challenges in that year), FlexTool assesses the flexibility of OSeMOSYS power system capacities and identifies additional power plant or transmission line capacities to solve the flexibility issues. These additional capacities are then fed back as constraints into OSeMOSYS, leading to a revised pathway for the power system capacities expansion. The process is then repeated for the next marker year. In this study, the chosen marker years were 2030 and 2050.

OSeMOSYS description

For details on the OSeMOSYS setup, the reader is referred to Kihara et al.²⁴. As compared to that publication, four main additional elements were included in OSeMOSYS as such, which are explored here.

The first is the inclusion of the geo-referenced solar and wind Model Supply Regions as separate technologies, replacing the former “generic” solar and wind investment option. Details are given below in “*Representation of solar and wind investment options*”.

The second is the inclusion of buildout speed constraints in each of the separate geo-referenced VRE clusters to ensure *N-1* security adherence²⁹, avoiding too high concentrations of VRE in areas evacuated by a single transmission corridor. Again, details are given below in “*Representation of solar and wind investment options*”.

The third adaptation is applied at the level of the time slice definition, and stems from the observation of high penetration of wind power in the results for the Kenyan context²⁴. Using time slices at seasonal and daily time scales allows to capture the main variabilities of demand, hydropower profiles, and solar resources, but it leaves out the substantial fluctuations of wind power yield at the “in-between” resolution of several days to weeks. Using classical seasonal and daily time slices can thus lead to averaging out any effect of prolonged periods with bad wind conditions (wind droughts, sometimes referred to as “*Dunkelflauten*” when concurrent with unfavourable solar conditions), which cannot be captured at daily or seasonal level but which would have strong impacts on system flexibility and reserve needs in practice. (How to better represent the possibility of such periods occurring, remains an ongoing area of study in capacity expansion modelling^{41–44}.)

The result is that wind power often appears to be a more stable power source in time-sliced results than it actually is, i.e. the variability of the wind resource is under-represented. In some cases, this can lead to wind power almost appearing as “baseload” technology, leading to unrealistic model results. One could solve this by modelling at full hourly resolution, but this is usually prohibitive computationally in long-term capacity expansion models. One potential way to address this in capacity expansion models without unduly burdening computational requirements is therefore to explicitly distinguish periods of low and high resource availability, inspired by e.g. refs.^{41–44}. This allows approximating the statistical properties of wind across time slices better.

Inspired by the above, here, we use a similar principle to better represent wind variability: adding a fifth “virtual season” to the time slices setup in OSeMOSYS to capture the potential effect of wind droughts (this approach works as long as the geographical area under consideration is not larger than typical weather systems, in which case it is no longer possible to define such a season for all regions under consideration.) This virtual season is defined to cover only the 10% “worst” wind days of the year, i.e. the 10% days with the lowest CF on average over all wind clusters weighted equally. This season is thus hypothetical in that it represents a non-chronological set of days. Within this season, no distinction is made between weekdays and weekend days. Correspondingly, all days selected for this season are removed from their original (chronological) season to avoid double-counting (see Table S3).

We note that this addition of a virtual weak wind season has a considerable effect on the representation of the wind resource: in that season, the average wind CF is typically only a fraction of its yearly average, representing truly bad wind conditions. A full table with the numbers per cluster is given in the Supplementary Material (see Table S4). We conclude that the inclusion of this season works well to explicitly represent the possibility of wind droughts in the Kenyan system.

The fourth adaptation refers to the explicit inclusion of costs for building an LNG terminal to have a more refined representation of the future costs of expanding natural gas-based power generation infrastructure. From 2030 onwards, it is considered that Kenya could add a maximum annual LNG import capacity of 1 Mton/year every five years, hence reaching a total maximum of 5 Mton/year by 2050. The cost of a 1 Mton/y import terminal is estimated to be of 570 MUSD, plus an additional investment of around 300 MUSD for the infrastructure needed to bring the regasified natural gas to the consumers (power plants). Such investment costs add up to a capacity cost for natural gas import infrastructure of approximately 29 MUSD/PJ/y.

FlexTool assumptions

The main assumptions in FlexTool are described in Kihara et al.²⁴. The technical and economic parameters of the power plants and transmission lines are aligned with OSeMOSYS. Values for the minimum loads per technology were provided by the LCPDP team, except for the case of geothermal, where the authors assumed a minimum load value of 75% to reflect a preference for baseload operation (see Table S2).

The contribution factor of solar and wind power to reserve provision was set to 50% of their hourly curtailed production (see Table S1). Reserves refer to capacity that will not be used for electricity generation, but that can provide upward operational capacity requirements in case of contingencies occurring in the power system.

Penalty costs associated with the different constraints of FlexTool are shown in Table S5. For each year, the inertia limit is computed using the following formula $\frac{f}{2} * P_{loss}/RoCoF$ with f the nominal frequency of the system (50 Hz for the Kenyan power system), P_{loss} the maximum power that could be lost and $RoCoF$ the rate of change of frequency. The Kenyan power system has not set a rate of change of frequency, but for this study, a value of 1 Hz/s has been assumed. As the maximum power loss changes based on the marker year, the inertia requirement also varies by year.

In our scenarios, P_{loss} typically corresponds to the total capacity located in a single VRE cluster selected by OSeMOSYS. For instance, in the 2050 low-demand case, the largest potential loss is 1.97 GW for several clusters for both solar and wind. This leads to an inertia constraint of 35.5 GWs. We deliberately adopt a conservative approach to ensure sufficient inertia for system reliability, although we acknowledge that wind power production fluctuates, and the maximum loss might be lower depending on the time slices in which the contingency happens.

Compared to the version described in Kihara et al.²⁴, Flextool has been disaggregated into four regions that correspond to the power system areas used by the LCPDP team in their medium and long-term plans^{30,31}: Western, Nairobi, Mt Kenya, Coast. All current and future power plants are thus associated with one of the four regions. Each solar and wind cluster is thus allocated to one region. For generic capacities of hydro, gas and batteries, which are not location-specific, the following assumptions apply: hydropower potential is assumed to be developed in Mt Kenya region, gas in the Coast, and batteries are installed for 75% in the Western region near solar and wind farms, with the remaining capacity in Nairobi. Imports are assumed to directly reach Nairobi.

The base year capacities for inter-regional transmission are provided by the LCPDP team for 2019. In dispatch mode, these capacities for the marker years remain unchanged compared to the base year. In investment mode, the maximum capacities of the different transmission lines increase over time as shown in Table S6.

Representation of solar and wind investment options

The geospatially differentiated representation of solar PV and wind power potential was based on the concept of “Model Supply Regions” (MSR) introduced by IRENA and published in Sterl et al.²⁸. Starting from existing maps on resource strength (irradiation, wind speed, etc.) and on geospatial limitations (conflicting land use, unfavourable slope, protected areas, high population densities, existing road/grid infrastructure, etc.), the MSR workflow allows to identify each country’s feasible regions for utility-scale VRE expansion. Through a statistical downscaling approach applied on reanalysis data, the MSR method combines the benefits of high spatial resolution of VRE potential (kilometre-scale, thus avoiding conflating regions with highly divergent strengths into the same “pixel”) with those of high temporal resolution (hourly).

Subsequently, the MSR workflow disaggregates the identified regions into individual units that represent potential individual power plants with maximum sizes ranging from several tens of MW to a few GW (depending on geographical constraints), each with their own capacity factors, hourly production profiles, and investment costs. Here, the latter reflect not only the costs for the plant itself, but also the required transmission line (and corresponding substation) buildout and road network buildout to connect the location to existing grid/road infrastructure. Each resulting individual unit is called a Model Supply Region, the smallest spatial unit that has unique techno-economic characteristics.

In principle, MSRs can be directly input into capacity expansion modelling, as the required techno-economic metadata is available and unique for each. However, there are usually thousands of such regions available at the country-level whose overall potential vastly outnumbers the projected future demand, potentially leading to overcomplicated models with high runtimes. Therefore, Sterl et al.²⁸ recommends two further steps to keep MSR-based models “light” in size.

The first step consists of ranking the MSRs according to a certain “attractiveness” criterion, such as the expected LCOE at the power plant level, and only including the most attractive segment in the capacity expansion model. For instance, Sterl et al.²⁸ recommended including only the top 5% (by LCOE, including transmission and road network expansion costs in the plant CAPEX) in terms of country area coverage.

The second step consists of using a mathematical *k*-means clustering method to group the remaining top MSRs (still typically up to several hundreds) into a limited number of “clusters”, each characterised by extremely similar shapes of the temporal production curves. (Given the typical decorrelation distance of VRE resources, this approach tends to create clusters made up of spatially contiguous

MSRs, though in some cases a single cluster could consist of different “islands” of very high and similar potential separated by areas of lower resource strength.) The idea is that, in terms of system planning, it would not matter a lot where exactly within the cluster future power plants would be built, as the individual locations within the cluster are of highly similar nature. Sterl et al.²⁸ recommended to group the MSRs into around 10 clusters for countries of a size like Kenya’s.

In this study, we followed the recommendations by Sterl et al.²⁸, including 10 clusters of solar PV MSRs and 10 clusters of wind MSRs as individual technologies in the OSeMOSYS-FlexTool workflow, each with their own unique profiles, investment costs, and maximum deployment potential. The original datasets are available on Zenodo³³. We also followed the recommendations by Sterl et al.²⁸ in allocating loss factors between the hourly profiles that the VRE plant produces and what eventually reaches the grid of 8% for solar PV (outage and inverter losses) and 17% for wind (outage, array and wake losses).

The clusters in Sterl et al.²⁸ were developed based on an assumed wind turbine hub height of 100 meters. Since Kenya's largest wind farm to date, the Lake Turkana Wind Power Project, used somewhat lower-hub wind turbines, we calibrated the cluster-level wind power generation profiles to LCPDP data with a constant ratio, represented by the ratio of average capacity factor between the LCPDP-delivered time series for Lake Turkana Wind Power Project on one hand, and the wind MSR #4 (in which the Lake Turkana Wind Power Project falls) on the other. This ratio turned out to be 0.85.

After having included the clusters and their profiles in the model workflow, using the aforementioned grid and road expansion CAPEX to distinguish the clusters from each other at the cost-level, the model required further adaptations to realistically represent power system expansion taking into account system security constraints. In particular, the model should be prevented from indiscriminately accumulating VRE capacity within the same cluster. The reason is that a high concentration of power generation capacity within the same geospatial zone, using (at least partly) the same evacuation infrastructure, would likely violate *N-1* constraints, as argued e.g. by Donk et al.²⁹. From a system security point-of-view, all capacity within a single cluster, assumed to be evacuated by the same transmission line, acts as a single power plant (even if, in reality, it could be made up of several different projects), and the potential loss of a single power plant should never exceed the reserve margin of the system for *N-1* security. Hence, the total allowed capacity within each cluster in any modelling year was constrained to a maximum corresponding to the reserve margin of the system (in MW) in that year (so long as that number did not exceed the maximum theoretical deployment potential in the cluster, in which case the latter number prevailed as overall ceiling). The reserve margin, in its turn, was set to 10% of the peak demand in each year.

Scenarios

Four scenarios have been modelled in this work, based on two different demand projections (referenced in this text as low and high demand) and two capital cost projections for solar and wind (again referenced in this text as low and high cost). The two demand projections considered are the ones used in Kihara et al.²⁴, and are based on the latest version of the Least Cost Power Development Plan, published in 2022⁴⁵. More details on demand profiles and total annual demand projections are given in section S1.1. Solar and wind capital costs are based on projected cost reductions taken from the IEA’s World Energy Outlook (WEO)⁴⁶. The low-cost scenario corresponds to the IEA’s Net Zero (NZ) scenario, while the high-cost one to the Stated Policy (SP) one. A complete description of how capital costs have been obtained is given in section S1.2. The resulting four scenarios are hence the following:

- S1 – Low demand, low solar and wind capital costs projections.
- S2 – High demand, low solar and wind capital costs projections.
- S3 – Low demand, high solar and wind capital costs projections.

- S4 – High demand, high solar and wind capital costs projections.

Resource availability

Lead contact

Further information and requests for resources and materials should be directed to and will be fulfilled by the Lead Contact, Pietro Lubello (p.lubello@ucl.ac.uk).

Materials availability

This study did not generate new unique materials.

Data and code availability

The OSeMOSYS model and data files used in this study can be found on the GitHub repository at: https://github.com/ClimateCompatibleGrowth/osemosys_kenya_psm, and the specific version of the model was released as v2.0.0: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11165893>. The FlexTool model is available online at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11165550>.

Supplemental information

Supplemental information to this paper contains the following data: Supplemental experimental procedures, Tables S1-S8 and Figures S1-S2.

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Author contributions

A.M. and P.L. carried out the modelling work with OSeMOSYS and FlexTool under the guidance of S.S., who conceived the study. E.M.T., M.M., and M.A. supported calibration of the models to the Kenyan context. All authors contributed to the drafting and reviewing of the manuscript.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Figure legends

Figure 1. Power system capacities and levels of activity in OSeMOSYS.

OSeMOSYS results for the low (left column) and high (right column) demand scenarios. The first row shows the evolution of the installed capacity throughout the modelled time horizon, while the second row does the same for the actual energy produced by each power source. Rows three and four show the amount of energy stored and discharged each year by, respectively, pumped hydro and batteries. See also Figure S1 for additional scenarios.

Figure 2. Geospatial representation of the solar and wind clusters for Kenya.

The figure shows the clusters for solar PV (left) and wind power (right) included in the present OSeMOSYS-FlexTool workflow. The data on clusters is taken from the repository in ref. ³³ and re-visualised for purposes of this paper. The data on transmission and distribution grid is taken from GridFinder ³⁴. Note that the numbers of the clusters are arbitrarily assigned and do not signify any particular order of attractiveness. Both sets of clusters cover 5% of Kenya's territory, and the total potential for solar PV and wind power plant deployment across clusters adds up to 96 GW (solar) and 86 GW (wind).

Figure 3. Capacity buildout of the geospatially referenced solar and wind clusters.

MSR cluster buildout according to OSeMOSYS for the low (left) and high (right) demand scenarios. The first row shows the solar MSR cluster buildout and the second row the wind MSR cluster buildout. See also Figure S2 for additional scenarios.

Figure 4. Additional generation capacities identified by FlexTool.

Additional generation capacities suggested by FlexTool for 2030 and 2050 on top of the OSeMOSYS results to deal with flexibility challenges at the dispatch level. There is also additional investment in transmission capacities between different regions of the Kenyan grid, which are described in the text but not shown here.

Figure 5. FlexTool dispatch profiles.

Dispatch of the power plants in the low-demand scenario for 2050, before (Base) and after (Invest) investments suggested by FlexTool.